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Environment

Effect of climatic changes on rice production in Punjab, India

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Global climatic changes are projected to influence crop production. We conducted a study to assess rice yields in Punjab, India, as a consequence of changing climate scenarios. Historical weather data for 1970-93 for Ludhiana were analyzed to determine trends in temperature and rainfall. Temperature increased consistently by about 0.3-0.5 °C but no trend was apparent for rainfall during this period (Fig.1). Global warming scenarios have predicted a temperature rise of 0.5-2.5 °C by the year 2030 and global increases in atmospheric CO₂ concentration.

We used rice growth simulation model CERES-rice. PR106, a commonly grown rice cultivar in the region, was used to validate it for local conditions. Using computer simulations, the yield under increasing temperature and CO₂ levels was evaluated and compared with normal temperature and CO₂ scenarios. We created future weather by increasing the daily temperature of the growing season by 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0 °C above normal, and using CO₂ concentrations of 330 (normal), 430, 530, and 630 ppm. The interactive effects of increase in temperature and CO₂ concentrations were also simulated to assess projected rice grain yield. Rice growth and yield were simulated under irrigated and no nutritional and pest stress conditions. As per normal practice, 40-d-old seedlings were transplanted on 15 Jun at 33 hills/m² using two seedlings per hill.

Under the normal temperature scenario, grain yield increased above the usual 7.0 t/ha by 2.6% with enhanced CO₂ concentrations of 430, 7.3% with 530 ppm, and 8.8% with 630 ppm (Fig. 2). Under normal CO₂ concentration, rice yield decreased by 4.4, 7.3, 9.4, 8.7, 14.2, and 24.5%, for temperature increments of

○ Annual deviation for mean temperature
 ■ 5-yr moving average for temperature
 ● Annual deviation for rainfall
 □ 5-yr moving average for rainfall

1. Deviation from normal temperature and rainfall, Ludhiana, India, 1972-92.

2. Effect of increasing CO₂ and temperature on grain yield of rice.

0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0 °C above normal, respectively. Adverse effects of temperature increases of nearly 0.3, 0.9, and 1.1 °C on rice yield were nullified by enhanced CO₂ concentrations of 430, 530, and 630 ppm, respectively. A World Meteorological Organization study predicted a global warming of 1.5-4.5 °C with doubling of CO₂ concentrations. Our results indicate that a near doubling of CO₂ will neutralize the negative effects on rice yields if the corresponding temperature increase is up to about 1.1 °C above normal. Global warming of 3.0 °C predicted for well into the 21st century could lead to drastic reductions in rice grain yields of 20.1% even with a CO₂ concentration of 630 ppm. Thus increase in CO₂ level would be beneficial for rice yields only if corresponding temperature rise is limited to about 1 °C above normal. ■

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